

THE USE OF THE WALKING IMPAIRMENT QUESTIONNAIRE (WIQ) IN PATIENTS WITH LOWER LIMB ISCHEMIA STAGE IIB ACCORDING TO THE FONTAINE CLASSIFICATION

**Żanna Fiodorenko-Dumas PhD, Marta Majewska Pulsakowska PhD,
Małgorzata Paprocka-Borowicz Prof., Ilias Dumas PhD**

Wroclaw Medical University, Department of Physiotherapy, Poland

Abstract

Chronic lower limb ischemia significantly impairs the everyday functioning of the patient as it progresses. Patients complain of the inability to walk longer distances, climb stairs or walk briskly.

The aim of this study was to assess the influence of chronic lower limb ischemia on the long-term results measured using the Walking Impairment Questionnaire (WIQ), as well as to establish a relationship between our results and selected variables, i.e. BMI (Body Mass Index), ICD (Intermittent Claudication Index), ACD (Absolute Claudication Index) and gender.

Materials and Methods.

The research group consisted of 50 individuals diagnosed with lower limb ischemia stage IIB according to the Fontaine classification. All of the patients experienced intermittent claudication after walking a distance of less than 200 m. The mean age was $64,4 \pm 6,0$ years for men ($n=38$) and $62,7 \pm 6,9$ years for women ($n=12$). BMI for both sexes was $27,1 \pm 4,1$ kg/m². The study used the WIQ questionnaire, which consists of 21 items and evaluates walking speed, walking distance and stair climbing. In order to obtain information concerning gender, age and BMI of the patients, an original survey was created and distributed. In addition, the patients were evaluated using the treadmill stress test, which helps to determine the severity of claudication among patients.

Results.

Our research showed no correlation between the WIQ score and the gender of the patient. A statistically significant correlation was found between ICD, ACD and WIQ scores ($\rho=0,760$, $\rho=0,770$). No relationship was observed between the BMI and WIQ score ($p=0,612$). Scores in the individual WIQ domains strongly correlated with the total score obtained in the questionnaire.

Conclusions.

The WIQ questionnaire proved to be a reliable tool for assessing motor function and disorders in patients with chronic lower limb ischemia. The results of the treadmill stress test complied with the score of the questionnaire. There was no correlation between the WIQ score and gender, as well as with the BMI of the patients.

Key words: WIQ, claudication, lower limb ischemia, walking

Introduction

In recent times, peripheral arterial diseases have increasingly become a focus of attention, including lower extremity arterial disease (LEAD-lower extremities coronary artery diseases). LEAD significantly increases the risk of death and is the leading cause of lower-extremity amputation. Ischemia and hypoxia of the limb's tissues stimulate endogenous compensating

processes, such as angiogenesis and arteriogenesis. Unfortunately, both of these processes are insufficient in terms of their ability to provide the tissues with an adequate amount of oxygen and nutrients (11,16). The diagnosis of this disease consists not only in imaging, interviewing and the measurement of the ankle-brachial index (ABI), but also of the evaluation of the claudication distance (ICD), which can be based on a subjective assessment by the patient

(obtained from the interview) or objective tools, such as the treadmill test in standardized conditions, or the 6 Minute Walk Test. Claudication is defined as the pain of lower extremities which occurs when walking and forces the patient to stop. The pain subsides after a short rest and reappears after resuming walking. In cities, the pain frequently forces a patient to stop in front of shop windows, hence the common name of the disease: "window-shoppers disease". The assessment of the distance that a person can walk without pain, as well as the total distance achievable despite the pain can help to understand the problem that the patient has in coping with it. The progression of the disease causes the lower limbs to lose muscle strength, and as a result, longer walks become impossible (4, 5). An easily visible symptom is the reduction in the weight and circumference of the limb. The skin is also affected: it becomes paler, cooler and thinner, and hair is scarcer. In advanced stages, slow-healing ulcers may occur. Another characteristic symptom is the weakening of the pulse on the limb affected. In a healthy person, the pulse should be easily palpable on all the arteries that lie close to the skin. When atherosclerotic process affects the vessels, their walls become rigid and the pulse becomes imperceptible. On the lower limb, the pulse should be felt in the groin, below the knee, on the lateral side of the ankle and on the dorsum of the foot. It is important to self-control the pulse in these locations (1, 7, 9, 15, 19).

Standard diagnostic methods are often complemented by standardized questionnaires, in which a patient subjectively evaluates the severity of the disease and indicates the domains of life that have become completely dominated by the ongoing pathological process, making it impossible for them to function normally. The Walking Impairment Questionnaire is one of many questionnaires designed to evaluate the severity of walking impairment as seen by the patient (13, 14).

The incidence of chronic lower limb ischemia depends on age. The majority of the patients are over 55 years old. Atherosclerotic lesions in abdominal aorta and arteries of the lower extremities are found in 20 percent of

Europeans and Americans in this age group. 30 percent of the population over 75 years of age is affected. Men are affected twice as often as women; however, in patients over 70 years of age as well as in patients with diabetes, the incidence is similar for both genders. 30,000 new cases are reported in Poland every year (3,5).

The aim of this study was to assess the influence of the chronic lower limb ischemia on the long-term results in the Walking Impairment Questionnaire (WIQ) as well as to establish a relationship between our results and selected variables, i.e. BMI (Body Mass Index), ICD (Intermittent Claudication Index), ACD (Absolute Claudication Index) and gender..

Materials and methods

The research group consisted of 50 individuals diagnosed with lower limb ischemia stage IIb according to the Fontaine classification. All of the patients presented claudication after walking a distance of less than 200 m. The mean age was 64,4±6,0 years for men (n=38) and 62,7±6,9 years for women (n=12). BMI for both sexes was 27,1±4,1 kg/m².

The exclusion criteria were as follows:

- trophic changes of the lower limbs,
- sensory disorders due to ischemia (sensory neuropathies) without intermittent claudication,
- comorbidities that permanently impair motor function,
- comorbidities that are contraindications for the stress test,
- lack of informed and voluntary consent for participation in the research project.

All of the patients were subjected to the treadmill stress test (a test which helps to evaluate the severity of claudication) with the treadmill moving at a constant speed of 3,2 km/h and with an inclination angle of 10 degrees. The patient was to identify the onset of pain due to ischemia caused by the stress test (ICD – Intermittent Claudication Index). The indication for the interruption of the test was the near-maximal pain that made it impossible for the patient to progress (ACD – Absolute Claudication Index). Persons qualifying for the stress test had their EKG assessed by a general practitioner before the test.

Furthermore, the patients completed a WIQ questionnaire (Walking Impairment Questionnaire) which consists of 21 items and evaluates walking speed, walking distance and stair climbing. The questionnaire, as well as the criteria of assessment, are available online at http://www.cebp.nl/vault_public/filesystem/?ID=1458.

In order to obtain information characterizing the group, the participants were also asked about their age, comorbidities, weight and height.

The study was approved by the Bioethics Committee of the Wrocław Medical University: 2, Pasteur Street.

The results obtained enabled determination of the mean, the standard deviation and the Spearman's rank correlation coefficient.

Results

Subject characteristics (sex, BMI and comorbidities) are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Subject characteristics

Mean values of the parameters in groups		
	female	male
gender	24% (n=12)	76% (n=38)
age	62,7± 6,9 years	64,4±6,0 years
BMI	27,1±4,1 kg/m ²	27,4±5,1 kg/m ²
comorbidities	Female and male	
diabetes mellitus	32,30% (n=21)	
hypertension	46,15% (n=30)	
history of stroke	7,7% (n=5)	
history of heart attack	12,30% (n=8)	
hypercholesterolemia	1,53% (n=1)	

There were more men than women in the research group; the age differed slightly between the genders; the mean age for women was 62,7±6,9 years and for men 64,4±6,0 years. BMI values were similar for both genders. The most frequent comorbidities were diabetes (21 answers – 32,30%) and hypertension (30 answers – 46,15%).

Table 2. The results of the tests performed

Results of the treadmill test and WIQ questionnaire		
	female	male
ICD	69,21±30,14 m	83,4±43,79 m
ACD	89,46±34,30 m	114,93±58,18 m
Total WIQ	0,688±0,103	0,706±0,130
speed	0,425±0,114	0,593±0,109
distance	0,725±0,052	0,725±0,809
stairs	0,792±0,107	0,794±0,115

The treadmill test enabled evaluation of the average distance after which pain appeared, as well as the sub-maximal pain being the indication for the interruption of the test. Female participants reported ischemic pain more quickly and ultimately covered shorter distances than male participants (89,46±34,30 m vs 114,93±58,18 m). The WIQ scores also differed between the genders, namely in the speed domain (0,425±0,114 vs 0,593±0,109). Other domains of the questionnaire did not differ significantly between the groups and gender did not have a significant impact on the scores (Table 2).

Table 3. The correlations of WIQ score with selected variables

			T_WIQ
Spearman's rho	ICD	Correlation coefficient	,760**
		Significance level (bilateral)	0,01
		N	50
	ACD	Correlation coefficient	,770**
		Significance level (bilateral)	0,01
		N	49
	BMI	Correlation coefficient	,073
		Significance level (bilateral)	,612
		N	50
	T_WIQ	Correlation coefficient	1,000
		Significance level (bilateral)	0,01.
		N	50

The analysis using Spearman's rank correlation coefficient indicated that there was a statistically significant correlation between the distance covered (ICD, ACD) and WIQ questionnaire score ($p < 0,01$). The higher the

ICD and ACD values, the higher the TWIQ (total WIQ). No correlations were found between the BMI of the participants and their TWIQ (Table 3).

Figure 1. Relationship between the age and the TWIQ score.

It can be noted that patients aged 56-65 scored highest in the TWIQ, whereas the youngest patients, aged 46-55, scored lowest. The differences, however, are not statistically significant (Fig. 1).

The individual components of the WIQ questionnaire, i.e. the walking distance, walking speed and stair climbing were in strong relationship with TWIQ, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Correlations between the individual WIQ domains with total WIQ score.

			T_WIQ
Spearman's rho	Distance	Correlation coefficient	,911**
		Significance level (bilateral)	0,05
		N	50
	Speed	Correlation coefficient	,890**
		Significance level (bilateral)	0,05
		N	50
	Stairs	Correlation coefficient	,833**
		Significance level (bilateral)	0,05
		N	50

Discussion

The development of atherosclerosis consists of two stages. Firstly, as a result of existing risk

factors, a dysfunction of endothelium occurs, which results in an increase of the permeability of the endothelium to lipoproteins, viruses and bacteria. Accumulating lipoproteins, mainly LDL

(*low density lipoproteins*), are absorbed by monocytes and macrophages and subsequently bound with collagen fibers. This stage is reversible. In the second stage, an atherosclerotic plaque is formed. It is initially unstable, but stabilizes and calcifies over time. Chronic lower limb ischemia develops over many years. Initially, the disease has no symptoms. The development of the disease is facilitated by the progress of civilization. In many cases, the critical changes in the arteries are the first incentive to undergo diagnosis and treatment (16, 17).

The time of intervention is chosen according to the patient's disability level, as well as the potential complications of invasive treatment and expected long-term outcome. Research has proved that the implementation of rehabilitation programs for patients with intermittent claudication leads to clinically significant improvement. Moreover, physical activity can also modify the risk factors of atherosclerosis. In order to provide patients with adequate training programs, their motor function must be evaluated (2, 12, 18). The Treadmill test is commonly used for this purpose. Not only is it a diagnostic element, but it also serves to assess the progress of rehabilitation.

Our study proved the treadmill test to be a reliable diagnostic tool. In the research group, patients with femoropopliteal occlusion covered on average 69,21 m (female) and 83,4 m (male) before reporting pain in the lower limbs. Participants covered 14 m (female) and 24 m (male) more before interrupting the test. Kowalski et al (6). also used the treadmill test to evaluate the differences between patients with chronic lower limb ischemia. They used the WIQ questionnaire to assess the individual components of locomotion, which allowed them to emerge domains of interest and assess the impact of training on them. Although our study did not evaluate the progress of rehabilitation, we did use the questionnaire to assess the motor function of our patients. Obtained scores differed between genders, especially in the speed domain. The WIQ speed score was $0,425 \pm 0,114$ for women and $0,593 \pm 0,109$ for men. Other domains, such as walking distance and stair climbing did not show statistically significant

differences between genders ($0,725 \pm 0,052$ in women vs $0,725 \pm 0,809$ in men; $0,792 \pm 0,107$ in women vs $0,794 \pm 0,115$ in men).

Mayers et al.(10) also used the WIQ questionnaire in their research. The mean age of the patients with chronic lower limb ischemia was $62,1 \pm 9,61$ years, the score in the distance domain was $0,55 \pm 0,42$, in the speed domain – $0,48 \pm 0,30$ and in the stairs domain – $0,56 \pm 0,47$.

McDemont's paper (8) randomized this questionnaire in a group of patients with chronic lower limb ischemia. The mean age was slightly higher than in our case ($71,7 \pm 9,8$ years). Diabetes was diagnosed in 28,1% of the patients. 21,2% of the respondents had a history of heart attacks. In our study, diabetes was found in 32,30% of the participants, whereas history of heart attacks – in 12,30% of the patients. In McDemont's research, scores in the individual domains were as follows: $0,409 \pm 0,307$ in the distance domain; $0,371 \pm 0,267$ in the speed domain; $0,489 \pm 0,296$ in the stairs domain. The researchers aimed at establishing a relationship between the results of the 6 Minute Walk Test and the WIQ score. The correlation was statistically significant – the longer the distance walked, the higher the WIQ score in all of the domains. A similar pattern was revealed in our study, as ICD and ACD values correlated positively with the total WIQ score.

No reports concerning the correlation of age or BMI with the WIQ score have been found in literature, which suggest that pain due to lower limb ischemia appears much earlier than discomfort caused by the age or weight of the respondents. Therefore, influence of these parameters on the results of the surveys assessing motor function of the lower limbs should not be expected.

Conclusions

1. Our research showed no correlation between the total WIQ score and gender.
2. There was a statistically significant correlation between the ICD and ACD indexes and the total WIQ score ($p=0,760$).
3. No statistically significant correlation was found between the BMI and the Total WIQ ($p=0,612$).

4. The scores in individual WIQ domains (distance, speed, stairs) strongly correlated with the total WIQ score ($p > 0,01$).

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Correspondence

Żanna Fiodorenko-Dumas

Department of Physiotherapy, Wrocław Medical University

2 Grunwaldzka Street; 50-355 Wrocław

Phone: +48605955424

E-mail: z.fiodorenko@poczta.onet.pl